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**GraspOS SCOPE+i
Resource:**

**Indicators guide 2:
Frameworks
and toolboxes
for open research**

**Actionable
version**

Definition

This resource outlines a process for choosing indicators aimed at assessing Open Research. The process relies on two concepts: an indicator framework and an indicator toolbox. The indicator framework is context-specific decision lens that sets out why, for whom, and under what conditions indicators will be used. Whereas, the indicator toolbox is the curated collection of potential indicators, qualitative and quantitative, organized and documented with the rationale for each selected indicator. The framework and toolbox work together. The indicator framework provides the strategy for selecting and using indicators, while the toolbox supplies and documents the chosen indicators and their application. This guide draws on the European Commission report: Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship (2019).

Relevant SCOPE stages

This resource is most relevant in SCOPE stages:

- (O) Options for evaluating and
- (P) Probe deeply

When and how to use

Developing an indicator framework for research evaluation requires careful consideration of multiple analytical dimensions related to the purpose and context of use. Engaging stakeholders in a reflective process to determine which indicators are most appropriate enhances the relevance, credibility, and utility of the evaluation. This guide offers a high-level overview of the considerations in preparing an indicator framework and indicator toolbox, with the recommendation that the process engages relevant stakeholders and practitioners such as: researchers, evaluators, data and metrics specialists, and policy or funding representatives.

Guidance

The following six steps guide the design of an indicator framework and the development of an indicator toolbox for an assessment in a specific context. Select the steps that fit the assessment. Each chosen step contributes to an overall strategy for indicator selection (the indicator framework). After the framework is finalized, indicators are collaboratively chosen and documented to create an indicator toolbox tailored to the assessment.

1. Clarify goal of assessment

- *Ask:* Why is an indicator needed?
- Monitoring → system-level trends using aggregate measures.
- Learning → context-rich, qualitative or mixed evidence.
- Resource allocation / career assessment → balance comparability with accuracy.
- *Action:* Define the main purpose to guide later indicator choices.

2. Identify values (from the SCOPE process)
 - *Ask:* Which SCOPE-derived values (e.g., equity, transparency) will anchor the assessment?
 - *Action:* Revisit the SCOPE discussions with stakeholders that lead to values. Articulate how each chosen value should shape research practices and evaluation goals. Map the identified sub-values to desired research practices (e.g., equity → global access and capacity building; transparency → reproducible workflows). Record the kinds of evidence that will later demonstrate these practices, without yet selecting specific indicators.
3. Specify level of assessment
 - *Ask:* At what level will indicators operate—system, organizational, or individual/group?
 - *Action:* Match indicator types to the chosen level and guard against misusing system-level metrics for individual evaluation.
4. Examine disciplinary and research approaches
 - *Ask:* How do methods and epistemic cultures shape openness?
 - *Action:* Capture relevant knowledge-creation and sharing modes; plan for co-design with the research community.
5. Map stakeholders, audiences, and beneficiaries
 - *Ask:* Whose engagement and benefit matter most (e.g., researchers, funders, citizens)?
 - *Action:* Plan indicators that can later show meaningful interactions and check for inclusiveness and potential bias.
6. Assess the research environment
 - *Ask:* Which enabling or constraining conditions apply (e.g., policies, infrastructure, funding)?
 - *Action:* Anticipate indicators that reflect environmental readiness or constraints and adjust expectations accordingly.

Further reading

SCOPE+i Resources

- Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>
- Guide on choosing an assessment method.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>
- Purpose and context statement template.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525469>

Other

- SCOPE Framework (INORMS 2023): <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>
- European Commission (2019): Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship.
<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/44528>

